

Potential clinical relevance of L-Carnitine supplementation in oncology

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Background

L-Carnitine (LC) is an endogenous molecule which is biosynthesized from L-lysine and L-methionine and involved in fatty acid metabolism. LC can be found in foods, but it is especially abundant in beef, lamb, fish, poultry and milk. LC transports the chains of fatty acids into the mitochondrial matrix, thus allowing the cells to break down fat and get energy from the stored fat reserves [1]. Carnitine is a conditionally essential nutrient. It is a vital factor for energy production and fatty acid metabolism. Carnitine deficiencies can be associated with genetic mutations of carnitine transporters or chronic diseases (liver and kidney disease). Aberrations of carnitine regulation with subsequent carnitine deficiency is associated with diabetes mellitus, sepsis, cardiomyopathy, protein-energy malnutrition, cirrhosis, various endocrine disorders and with aging. It has been found that nutritional supplementation of LC might be helpful for uremic patients, as a complementary therapy for neuropathic pain, or in diabetic patients. Still, it is a life-saving therapy in primary carnitine deficiency. LC supplementation (LCS) is also investigated in Alzheimer's disease and hepatic encephalopathy. It has been observed that topical application of LC in dry eye syndrome is osmoprotective and it also modulates immune and inflammatory responses. There is some evidence in the available scientific literature supporting that LCS may be beneficial in cardiovascular diseases and obesity. There is also some evidence showing the association improved glucose intolerance and total energy expenditure [2].

LCS might also be considered for the patients undergoing cancer chemotherapy because it is cheap. There is some evidence showing that it can reduce chemotherapy-induced multiple organ toxicity and chemotherapy-associated general fatigue. Studies have also shown that LCS helps maintain plasma albumin levels and lymphocyte counts during chemotherapy. These are important in preventing increased susceptibility to various bacterial, viral, and fungal infections, including opportunistic pathogens, associated with chemotherapy. As LCS might improve the tolerability of chemotherapy, it could mitigate adverse effects of chemotherapy and help main the optimal dose of chemotherapeutic agents thorough the cycle, allowing more cancer cells to be destroyed. This could potentially increase the patient's chances for survival. There is also some evidence that LC inhibits cancer cell growth both *in vitro* and *in vivo*, meaning that LC could be considered as a complementary chemotherapeutic agent as well, but more preclinical and clinical evidence is necessary to determine the exact clinical relevance and efficacy of LCS in oncology.

LCS in oncology

Based on experimental and clinical data reviewed by Sayed-Ahmed, LCS could be helpful when given along with doxorubicin, cisplatin, carboplatin, oxaliplatin, cyclophosphamide and ifosfamide [3]. LCS in chemotherapy could mitigate multiple organ toxicities, permit the maintenance of the optimal dose thorough the cycle and consequently increase the rate of cancer cells death, increase the tolerability of chemotherapeutic regime and increase the survival rate. It seems that it is especially beneficial when paired with platinum derivatives, but it

could also be useful as nutritional support in the doxorubicin-, cyclophosphamide- and ifosfamide-based chemotherapies.

Matsui and coworkers investigated the study of 11 cancer patients (4 men, 7 women) on chemotherapy suffering from general fatigue, the role of LCS and its effects on general fatigue associated with chemotherapy. LC deficiency, which is often developed during chemotherapy, is considered to be a factor contributing to general fatigue. The chemotherapy regimens for colorectal cancer (8 patients) were: FOLFIRI (leucovorin, fluorouracil, irinotecan) + bevacizumab (3 patients), FOLFOX (leucovorin, fluorouracil, oxaliplatin; 2 patients), FOLFOX + bevacizumab (1 patient), FOLFIRI + panitumumab (1 patient) and TAS-102 (oral fixed-dose formulation of trifluorothymidine and tipiracil; 1 patient). The chemotherapy regimens used for pancreatic cancer (2 patients) were S-1 (oral dihydropyrimidine dehydrogenase inhibitory fluoropyrimidine-based on a biochemical modulation of 5-fluorouracil, tegafur, 5-chloro-2, 4-dihydropyridine, potassium oxonate) and gemcitabine + nab-paclitaxel. The chemotherapy administered for biliary tract cancer (1 patient) was gemcitabine + cisplatin. LCS (1500 mg/day of levocarnitine peroral during 8 weeks) reduced general fatigue in all cases, maintained the plasma albumin levels and lymphocyte counts during chemotherapy, and enabled patients to continue chemotherapy sequentially without dose reduction [4]. This study showed that LCS might reduce chemotherapy-associated general fatigue, which is one of the most important factors in the tolerability chemotherapeutic regimes, and therefore allow the conduction of chemotherapeutic regimes without the need for dose reduction. Second, patients receiving LCS maintained the plasma albumin levels, which is also very important, first, because oedemas caused by hypoalbuminemia severely impact the patient's quality of life (QoL) and second, binding of the chemotherapeutic drug to albumin is vital for the transport, distribution and metabolism of the drug. Therefore, low albumin levels are associated with impaired metabolism of chemotherapeutic drugs. Third, patients receiving LCS maintained the lymphocyte counts during chemotherapy which is a crucial factor in preventing infections that usually occur as a consequence of chemotherapy-induced leukopenia and lymphocytopenia. All of this together can improve the efficacy of chemotherapy, QoL and survival rate.

Kraft and coworkers found in a prospective, multi-center, placebo-controlled, randomized and double-blinded trial, including 72 patients with advanced pancreatic cancer that patients with pancreatic cancer may have a clinically relevant benefit from the peroral LCS: during treatment body-mass-index in LC group (4 g of oral LC for 12 weeks) increased by $3.4 \pm 1.4\%$ and decreased ($-1.5 \pm 1.4\%$) in controls ($p < 0.05$); nutritional status (body cell mass, body fat) and QoL parameters improved under LC; and there was a trend towards increased overall survival in the LC group (median 519 ± 50 days versus 399 ± 43 days, statistically not significant) and towards a reduced hospital-stay (36 ± 4 days versus 41 ± 9 days, statistically not significant) [5]. This study showed that patients receiving LCS had a better nutritional status which is also a very important factor in oncology. Patients that suffer from malnutrition, especially protein-malnutrition, and which can occur as a consequence of

chemotherapy, are less likely to endure the strenuous chemotherapeutic regime. Better nutritional status is also associated with beneficial psychological effects and better QoL. The study also showed that, although not statistically significant, there was an increased overall survival in the LC group and that there was a trend towards a reduced hospital stay.

Based on the Warburg's theory that most cancer cells mainly depend on glycolysis for ATP generation, LC treatment would theoretically lead to disturbance of cellular metabolism and cytotoxicity in cancer cells. In the study (Huang and coworkers), researchers found that: LC treatment selectively inhibits cancer cell growth *in vitro* and *in vivo*; LC treatment selectively induces the expression of p21^{cip1} gene, mRNA and protein in cancer cells but not p27^{kip1}; LC increases histone acetylation and induces accumulation of acetylated histones both in normal thymocytes and cancer cells; LC directly inhibits histone deacetylase (HDAC) I/II activities via binding to the active sites of HDAC and induces histone acetylation and lysine-acetylation accumulation *in vitro*; LC treatment induces accumulation of acetylated histones in chromatin associated with the p21^{cip1} gene but not p27^{kip1} detected by ChIP assay. In summary, the authors concluded these data support that LC, besides transporting acyl group, works as an endogenous HDAC inhibitor in the cell, thus showing the ability of cancer cell proliferation inhibition and induction of cancer cell death [6]. This study showed that LCS could not only be helpful as nutritional support, but it could also have a direct anti-cancer activity, therefore it could act as a complementary anti-cancer agent to standard chemotherapeutic regime, but more preclinical research on this subject is necessary to better investigate the actual chemotherapeutic potential of LC.

In another study, the chemo-preventive and angiopreventive activities of Acetyl-L-carnitine (ALCAR) were investigated *in vitro* on four different prostate cancer (PCa) cell lines (PC-3, DU-145, LNCaP, 22Rv1) and benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) cell line using flow cytometry (FC), and functional analysis of cell adhesion, migration and invasion (Boyden chambers). ALCAR modulation of surface antigen receptor (chemokines) and intracellular cytokine production was assessed by FC. The release of pro-angiogenic factors was detected by a multiplex immunoassay. The effects of ALCAR on PCa cell growth *in vivo* was investigated using tumor xenografts. Results showed that ALCAR reduces cell proliferation, induces apoptosis, hinders the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α and IFN- γ) and of chemokines CCL2, CXCL12 and receptor CXCR4 involved in the chemotactic axis and impairs the adhesion, migration and invasion capabilities of PCa and BPH cells *in vitro*. ALCAR exerts angiopreventive activities on PCa by reducing production/release of pro-angiogenic factors (VEGF, CXCL8, CCL2, angiogenin) and metalloprotease MMP-9. Exposure of endothelial cells to conditioned media from PCa cells, pre-treated with ALCAR, inhibited the expression of CXCR4, CXCR1, CXCR2 and CCR2 compared to those from untreated cells. Oral administration of ALCAR to mice xenografted with two different PCa cell lines resulting in reduced tumor cell growth *in vivo* [7]. This study offers a significant preclinical evidence supporting the thesis of LC being not only beneficial as a nutritional agent, but as a complementary chemotherapeutic agent as well, especially in the reduction of here-studied prostate cancer cells growth, but a well-designed multicentric double-blind randomized clinical trial on prostate cancer patients, who would receive LCS along with standard prostate cancer therapeutic regime in comparison with a control group that would receive placebo along with standard prostate cancer therapeutic regime, would reveal whether these preclinical findings have clinical significance or not.

A study, designed to specify the role of LC in the pathogenesis of endometrial cancer by comparing the serum total LC levels of endometrial cancer patients (endometrioid-type endometrial cancer, n = 20) with those of healthy women (n = 20) who were matched with respect to age and body mass index, showed that serum total LC levels of women with endometrial cancer were significantly lower than those of healthy women ($5,519.4 \pm 2,712.5$ vs $7,940.8 \pm 3,566.6$ ng/dL, $P = 0.021$). Serum total L-carnitine levels decreased significantly and

progressively with advancing stage (stage I vs II vs III vs IV; $6,294.0 \pm 2,885.1$ vs $5,800.0 \pm 441.2$ vs $4,016.0 \pm 2,833.3$ vs $2,560.0 \pm 67.9$ ng/dL; $P = 0.021$) [8]. This clinical study showed that there is an inversely proportionate relationship between serum total LC levels and the stage of endometrial cancer, as well as it showed that serum LC levels were lower in women with endometrial cancer in comparison to those of healthy women, which raises two scientific questions: whether the normal LC body levels have a chemo-preventive role and can LS deficiency be considered as an independent risk factor for cancer. Based on these findings it would be interesting to design a large multicentric double-blind randomized clinical trial, in which one group of endometrial cancer patients would receive LCS along with standard endometrial cancer therapeutic regime and control group would receive placebo along with standard endometrial cancer therapeutic regime, in order to determine whether LCS could have a clinical relevance in the treatment endometrial cancer or not.

Watanabe and coworkers performed a randomized controlled clinical trial in which untreated patients with advanced gastric cancer were included. The primary endpoint was brief fatigue inventory (BFI). Patients were categorized into 2 groups: those who received LC oral supplements (group C) and those who did not (group N). Results showed that the serum carnitine levels were improved significantly in group C compared with group N. BFI was more aggravated in group N than group C, but the difference was not significant. Authors concluded that they could not demonstrate the effectiveness of LCS in the treatment of fatigue associated with chemotherapy in patients with gastric cancer [9].

A literature review (El-Ashmawy, Khalil) highlighted the possible role of LC as an add-on therapy to breast cancer patients maintained on tamoxifen. Authors suggested that LCS could be recommended to breast cancer patients starting tamoxifen treatment based on the substantial evidence of LC-associated improvements of tamoxifen-related side effects, better cancer prognosis by reducing the risk of developing cancer recurrence or metastasis, and overcoming tamoxifen resistance [10]. This literature review highlights the potential role of LCS in breast cancer patients on tamoxifen with potential benefits associated with better cancer prognosis and prevention of tamoxifen resistance, but more clinical studies are necessary in order to investigate whether LCS can lower the risks for breast cancer relapse and tamoxifen resistance.

L-acetyl-carnitine (LAC) has demonstrated beneficial effects on counteracting Chemotherapy-Induced Peripheral Neuropathy (CIPN) *in vitro* and in animal studies. Data from clinical trials showed that CIPN-patients treated with Taxane showed no benefit from LAC treatment [11, 12], but CIPN-patients treated with platinum compounds exhibited significant improvement of CIPN-related symptoms [13]. Available evidence is showing that LCS could be beneficial in the prevention and treatment of CIPN associated with platinum compounds, but more clinical research is mandatory in order to distinguish whether this effect is superior to placebo or not.

Conclusion

Evidence from the available literature about the potential clinical significance of LCS in oncology signals that LC could be considered for patients undergoing cancer chemotherapy, especially with doxorubicin, cisplatin, carboplatin, oxaliplatin, cyclophosphamide and ifosfamide, and for patients with breast cancer on tamoxifen, whilst patients treated with taxanes might not benefit from it, but larger, multicentric placebo-controlled randomized clinical trials are necessary to better investigate the role of LCS in oncology. Based on the results obtained from above-mentioned preclinical and small clinical studies, it would be feasible to investigate in a large multicentric placebo-controlled randomized clinical trials the potential benefit of LCS in the treatment of colorectal, breast, pancreatic, biliary, prostate and endometrial cancer. LCS is cheap, available up-to-date literature showed that it could reduce chemotherapy-induced multiple organ toxicity and

chemotherapy-associated general fatigue, some evidence also showed that it could help to maintain the plasma albumin levels and lymphocyte counts during chemotherapy, and there is some evidence that LC inhibits cancer cell growth both *in vitro* and *in vivo*, all of which together could promote the use of LCS in oncology. Chemotherapy-associated general fatigue is one of the most important factors in the tolerability of chemotherapeutic regimes, and therefore prevention and/or mitigation of general fatigue would allow the conduction of chemotherapeutic regime without the need for dose reduction, allowing more cancer cells to be destroyed and therefore, increasing the survival rate. Maintenance of normal albumin plasma levels is important for the prevention of hypoalbuminemia-associated oedemas, which have a negative effect on the QoL, and for the preservation of normal metabolism of chemotherapeutic drugs. Maintenance of normal lymphocyte count is important for the prevention of chemotherapy-associated increased susceptibility for various bacterial, viral and fungal infections, including opportunistic pathogens, which is an important factor in both survival and QoL. To summarize, the rationale of implementing LCS in oncology is to increase the tolerability of chemotherapy, thus mitigating the adverse effects of chemotherapy and maintaining the optimal dose of chemotherapeutic agents thorough the cycle, which allows more cancer cells to be destroyed whilst maintaining a lean body mass, and finally increasing chances of patient's survival and QoL. Cancer therapy needs multidisciplinary approaches with clinical nutritionists playing an important role. Good nutritional status is associated with beneficial psychological effects, which is also an important factor for the improvement of QoL, improvement and maintenance of motivation for treatment and improvement of psychological tolerability of the very complex and tiring cancer therapy.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

LC, L-Carnitine; LCS, LC supplementation; QoL, quality of life; HDAC, histone deacetylase; ALCAR, PCa, Acetyl-L-carnitine; prostate cancer ; BPH, benign prostatic hyperplasia; FC, flow cytometry; BFI, brief fatigue inventory; LAC, L-acetyl-carnitine; CIPN, Chemotherapy-Induced Peripheral Neuropathy.

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